

Thermal Retrogression Study of *N,N'*-Substituted-thioureas

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o-Aminoacetanilide (1) smoothly reacts in cold with phenyl and allyl isothiocyanates to give the corresponding thioureas (2), which on heating give 2-mercaptobenzimidazoles (8).

THIS paper reports the thermal behaviour of *N,N'*-disubstituted-thioureas (2) leading to the synthesis of 2-mercaptobenzimidazoles (8; Scheme 1). Phenyl and allyl isothiocyanate when condensed with *o*-aminoacetanilides (1a-d)^{1,2,8} at room temperature, yielded thioureas (2a-h, Table 1).

with those obtained from 2a-d respectively. This observation showed that *N*-aryl-*N'*-phenylthioureas (2a-d) are less stable than the *N*-aryl-*N'*-allylthioureas (2e-h). The conversion of the thioureas (2) to the benzimidazoles involved the retrogressive cleavage followed by cyclisation (Scheme 1). An

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THIOUREAS (2)* AND 2-MERCAPTOBENZIMIDAZOLES (8)**

Compd. no.	R ¹	R ²	Yield %	M.p. °C
2a	H	C ₆ H ₅	90	149
2b	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	80	145
2c	OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	83	131
2d	OC ₂ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	60	136
2e	H	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	80	162
2f	CH ₃	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	85	165
2g	OCH ₃	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	70	161
2h	OC ₂ H ₅	CH ₂ CH=CH ₂	62	144
8a	H	—	70(67)	299
8b	CH ₃	—	68(75)	287
8c	OCH ₃	—	65(72)	256
8d	OC ₂ H ₅	—	62(79)	245

*Thioureas 2a-d could not be crystallised because they underwent thermal retrogression, thioureas 2e-h were crystallised from ethanol-benzene.

**2-Mercaptobenzimidazole 8a-d were crystallised from benzene-ethanol (1:1), yields reported in parenthesis obtained via route (ii).

All compounds gave satisfactory C H and N analyses.

During repeated crystallisation of the thioureas (2a-d) for purification, in each case we got a high melting product in good yield. Also during the melting point determination of the thioureas, all the compounds melted and then solidified immediately. These observations prompted us to study the thermal behaviour of the thioureas (2a-h). The thioureas (2a-d) on heating under reflux in ethanol for 2 h produced the benzimidazoles (8a-d), whereas the thioureas (2e-h) survived similar treatment even for longer time. However, the thioureas (2e-h) on heating at 5-10° above their melting points, followed by the treatment with ethanol or chloroform, produced the benzimidazoles (8a-d) identical

alternative mechanism for the formation of benzimidazoles via the intermediates **9** and **10** is ruled out on the basis that when the thioureas (**2a-h**) were heated at 5–10° above their m.p.s. and then treated with chloroform, then the benzimidazoles (**8a-d**) and not the corresponding *N*-acetyl derivatives (**9**) were isolated.

When *o*-aminoacetanilide (**1**) and allyl isothiocyanate were condensed in hot ethanol, the thioureas (**2e-h**) were obtained, but when *o*-aminoacetanilide (**1**) and phenyl isothiocyanate were heated in ethanol, the 2-mercaptobenzimidazoles (**8**) were obtained (supported by ir, nmr, mass and elemental analyses data).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were run on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord-137 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra on a Varian HA-60 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard and mass spectra on a Varian Mat CH-7 spectrometer.

Condensation of *o*-aminoacetanilide (1**) with phenyl and allyl isothiocyanate:** A solution of *o*-aminoacetanilide (**1**, $R^1=H$; 1.50 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) was cooled to 20° and to it was added phenyl isothiocyanate (1.35 g, 0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 0.5 h and then allowed to stand. After 2 h a white product started separating out and the reaction contents were allowed to stand overnight. The resulting solid was then washed with ethanol and air-dried to afford the thiourea (**2a**, $R^1=H$, $R^2=C_6H_5$; 2.56 g, 90%), m.p. 149° (Found: C, 63.00; H, 5.15; N, 14.80. $C_{15}H_{15}N_3SO$ calcd. for: C, 63.15; H, 5.26; N, 14.73%); ν_{max} 3 400–3 200 (NH), 1 670 (C=O) and 1 550 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ (100 MHz; DMSO) 2.00 (3H, s, $CH_3-C=O$), δ 8.8 (1H, s, NH-C=O), 7–7.7 (9H, m, ArH) and 3.2–3.4 (2H, both the NH groups of thiourea overlapping each other).

Similarly other thioureas (**2b-d**) were prepared (Table 1).

o-Aminoacetanilide (**1**, $R^1=H$; 1.50 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (20 ml) was cooled to 20° and to it was added allyl isothiocyanate (0.99 g, 0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 h and then allowed to stand. After 8 h a white product separated out and the contents were further allowed to stand for 24 h. The resulting white solid was crystallised from C_6H_6 -ethanol mixture to afford *N*-substituted-*N'*-allyl thiourea (**2e**, $R^1=H$, $R^2=CH_2-CH=CH_2$; 2.00 g, 80%), m.p. 162°

(Found: C, 57.73; H, 6.15; N, 17.00. $C_{17}H_{15}N_3SO$ calcd. for: C, 57.83; H, 6.02; N, 16.86%); ν_{max} 3 300–3 200 (NH), 3 050 ($CH=CH_2$), 1 660 (C=O) and 1 560 cm^{-1} (aromatic); *m/e* 249 (27%).

Similarly other thioureas (**2f-h**) were prepared (Table 1).

The thioureas (**2a-d**) were not crystallised because on heating they underwent retrogressive cleavage followed by cyclisation to the corresponding 2-mercaptobenzimidazoles (**8a-d**). The crude products (**2a-d**) on washing with ethanol gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

2-Mercaptobenzimidazoles (8a-d**):** (i) *N*-Substituted-*N'*-phenylthiourea (**2a**, $R^1=H$, $R^2=C_6H_5$; 2.85 g, 0.01 mol) was heated in a sulphuric acid bath at 150° for 20 min when it first melted and then solidified immediately. The solidified product was crystallised from C_6H_6 -ethanol mixture to afford 2-mercaptobenzimidazole (**8a**, $R^1=H$; 1.34 g, 70%), m.p. 299° (Found: C, 56.15; H, 4.09; N, 18.41; S, 21.51. $C_7H_6N_2S$ calcd. for: C, 56.00; H, 4.00; N, 18.66; S, 21.33%); ν_{max} 3 300 (NH) and 1 500 cm^{-1} (aromatic); δ (100 MHz; DMSO) 3.5 (1H, s, NH), 12.5 (1H, s, SH) and 7.0–7.5 (4H, m, ArH); *m/e* 150 (100%). The structure was further confirmed by undepressed m.m.p. with authentic^a sample.

(ii) *N*-Substituted-*N'*-allylthiourea (**2e**, $R^1=H$, $R^2=CH_2-CH=CH_2$; 2.4 g, 0.01 mol) was heated in a sulphuric acid bath at 170° for 20 min, when it melted and then solidified at once. The solid product was crystallised⁴ from C_6H_6 -ethanol to afford 2-mercaptobenzimidazole (**8a**, $R^1=H$; 1.28 g, 67%), m.p. 299° (Found: C, 56.15; H, 4.09; N, 18.41; S, 21.51. $C_7H_6N_2S$ calcd. for: C, 56.00; H, 4.00; N, 18.66; S, 21.33%).

Other thioureas (**2a-h**) also underwent retrogressive cleavage followed by cyclisation to the corresponding 2-mercaptobenzimidazoles (**8a-d**; Table 1). The compounds gave undepressed m.m.p. and superimposable ir spectra.

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